

Analysis of Gestational Diabetes Mellitus from a Tertiary Care HospitalDivyanjali Singh¹, Richa Jha², Rakesh Ranjan³¹Tutor, Department of Anatomy, Government Medical College and Hospital, Purnea, Bihar, India²Assistant Professor, Department of Obstetrics & Gynaecology, Government Medical College and Hospital, Purnea, Bihar, India³Assistant Professor, Department of Anatomy, Government Medical College and Hospital, Purnea, Bihar, India

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Corresponding Author: Dr. Divyanjali Singh

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Abstract:**Background:** Gestational diabetes mellitus (GDM) is a significant health concern affecting pregnant women worldwide, with rising prevalence due to increasing maternal age, obesity, and changes in diagnostic criteria. GDM is associated with adverse maternal and neonatal outcomes, necessitating effective screening, management, and follow-up strategies.**Aim:** The aim of this study is to analyze the prevalence, risk factors, and outcomes of (GDM) in a tertiary care hospital.**Methods:** This prospective observational study was conducted over six months (October 2023 to March 2024) at the Obstetrics and Gynaecology Department, G.M.C.H. Purnea. A total of 200 pregnant women diagnosed with GDM were enrolled. Data on demographic details, medical history, clinical findings, and laboratory results were collected. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 23.0 to identify significant associations between GDM and various risk factors.**Results:** The study found that the mean age of participants was 29.5 years, with a mean BMI of 27.8 kg/m². Key risk factors included a family history of diabetes (30%) and previous GDM (20%). Maternal outcomes showed that 25% required insulin therapy, and 10% developed hypertensive disorders. Cesarean delivery was performed in 30% of cases. Fetal outcomes indicated an average birth weight of 3.2 kg, with 5% having low Apgar scores and 7.5% experiencing neonatal hypoglycemia. Significant associations were observed between GDM and family history of diabetes (p=0.03) and previous GDM (p=0.01).**Conclusion:** The study highlights the importance of targeted screening and management strategies for GDM, especially among high-risk populations. Early detection and intervention are crucial to improving maternal and fetal health outcomes.**Recommendations:** Enhanced screening protocols, particularly for high-risk groups, and comprehensive postpartum care are recommended to mitigate the long-term risks associated with GDM.**Keywords:** Gestational Diabetes Mellitus, Risk Factors, Maternal Outcomes, Fetal Outcomes, Screening.

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Introduction

(GDM) is a prevalent and growing concern in maternal-fetal medicine, affecting approximately 7-10% of pregnancies globally. It is characterized by glucose intolerance first recognized during pregnancy and has significant implications for both maternal and neonatal health. Recent studies have underscored the rising incidence of GDM, which can be attributed to factors such as increasing maternal age, obesity, and changes in diagnostic criteria [1].

A complicated interaction of hormonal, genetic, and environmental variables is involved in the pathogenesis of GDM. During pregnancy, the placenta produces hormones that can lead to insulin resistance, necessitating increased insulin

production to maintain normoglycemia. When the pancreatic beta cells cannot compensate for this increased demand, hyperglycemia ensues, leading to GDM. This condition is associated with various adverse outcomes, including macrosomia, preeclampsia, and an increased risk of cesarean delivery for the mother, as well as hypoglycemia, jaundice, and respiratory distress syndrome for the newborn [2].

The best methods for GDM screening and diagnosis have been the subject of recent studies. The American College of Obstetricians and Gynaecologists (ACOG) suggests a two-step screening procedure: a 50-gram glucose challenge test for initial screening, and a 100-gram oral

glucose tolerance test for confirmation in cases when the patient's blood glucose level is elevated. The best screening criteria are still up for debate, though, as some research indicates that screening more frequently and earlier may be more beneficial for maternal and foetal outcomes, especially for high-risk populations [2].

Management of GDM typically involves lifestyle interventions such as dietary modifications and physical activity, with insulin therapy or oral hypoglycemic agents used when necessary. Recent advances have explored the role of continuous glucose monitoring (CGM) in improving glycemic control and pregnancy outcomes. A study published in *Endocrine Reviews* highlighted the benefits of CGM in reducing the incidence of neonatal hypoglycemia and improving overall maternal glucose levels [3].

Moreover, GDM affects women and their children in the long run. In later life, women with a history of gestational diabetes mellitus (GDM) are at a notably higher risk of acquiring type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) and cardiovascular illnesses. Moreover, there is an increased incidence of T2DM, obesity, and metabolic syndrome in offspring. Therefore, long-term follow-up and postpartum screening are essential elements of GDM therapy [3].

The aim of this study is to analyze the prevalence, risk factors, and outcomes of gestational diabetes mellitus (GDM) in a tertiary care hospital.

Methodology

Study Design: This study is a prospective observational study conducted over a period of six months, from October 2023 to March 2024.

Study Setting: The study was carried out in the Obstetrics and Gynaecology Department at G.M.C.H. Purnea, a tertiary care hospital.

Participants: A total of 200 pregnant women diagnosed with (GDM) participated in the study.

Inclusion Criteria:

1. The International Association of Diabetes and Pregnancy Study Groups (IADPSG) criteria were used to diagnose GDM in pregnant women.
2. Patients aged between 18 and 45 years.
3. Singleton pregnancies.
4. An eagerness to take part in the research and give informed permission.

Exclusion Criteria:

1. Pre-existing diabetes mellitus.

2. Multiple pregnancies.
3. Severe comorbid conditions (e.g., chronic renal disease, chronic liver disease).
4. Patients on medications known to affect glucose metabolism (other than insulin).
5. Patients who did not provide consent.

Bias: To minimize selection bias, participants were consecutively enrolled based on the inclusion and exclusion criteria. To reduce information bias, standardized data collection procedures were employed. Observer bias was minimized by training the research team on uniform data collection techniques.

Data Collection: Data were collected using a structured questionnaire and hospital records. Information on demographic details, medical history, obstetric history, clinical examination findings, and laboratory results was obtained.

Procedure

1. **Enrollment:** Eligible participants were enrolled during their routine antenatal visits.
2. **Informed Consent:** Written informed consent was obtained from each participant.
3. **Clinical Assessment:** Detailed history and clinical examination were conducted.
4. **Laboratory Investigations:** Fasting blood glucose, oral glucose tolerance test (OGTT), and HbA1c levels were measured.
5. **Follow-up:** Participants were monitored throughout their pregnancy for maternal and fetal outcomes.

Statistical Analysis: Using SPSS version 23.0, data were analysed after being entered into Microsoft Excel. We summarised the data using descriptive statistics. Standard deviation (SD) and frequency were used to express categorical variables, whereas mean $\pm$ SD was used for continuous variables. To evaluate the relationship between GDM and other risk factors, inferential statistics were employed, such as the t-test for continuous variables and the Chi-square test for categorical ones. For statistical significance, a p-value of less than 0.05 was used.

Results

Demographic and Clinical Characteristics

The study involved 200 pregnant women who had been diagnosed (GDM). The participants' average age was 29.5 years (SD $\pm$ 5.3 years). Seventy percent of the participants fell within the 25–35 age range. A BMI of 27.8 kg/m² (SD $\pm$ 4.5 kg/m²) was the average.

Table 1: Demographic, Clinical Characteristics, and Risk Factors

Variable	Frequency (%) / Mean $\pm$ SD
Age Distribution (years)	
18-24	40 (20%)
25-35	140 (70%)
>35	20 (10%)
BMI (kg/m ²)	27.8 $\pm$ 4.5
Gravidity	
Primigravida	80 (40%)
Multigravida	120 (60%)
Risk Factors	
Family History of Diabetes	60 (30%)
Previous History of GDM	40 (20%)
PCOS	30 (15%)
Hypertension	25 (12.5%)
Blood Glucose Levels	
Fasting Blood Glucose (mg/dL)	95.2 $\pm$ 10.1
2-hour Post-OGTT (mg/dL)	153.4 $\pm$ 20.3

Table 2: Maternal and Fetal Outcomes

Outcome	Frequency (%) / Mean $\pm$ SD
Maternal Outcomes	
Insulin Therapy	50 (25%)
Hypertensive Disorders	20 (10%)
Cesarean Delivery	60 (30%)
Vaginal Delivery	140 (70%)
Fetal Outcomes	
Birth Weight (kg)	3.2 $\pm$ 0.5
Low Apgar Score (<7 at 5 min)	10 (5%)
Neonatal Hypoglycemia	15 (7.5%)
NICU Admission	20 (10%)
Association with GDM	p-value
Family History of Diabetes	0.03
Previous History of GDM	0.01
PCOS	0.08

The study discovered a substantial correlation between GDM and a prior history of GDM and a family history of diabetes, indicating that these variables may be critical in the development of GDM. The outcomes for mothers and foetuses made clear how important it is to control GDM well in order to minimise negative effects. The results highlight how crucial early identification and treatment are to the management of GDM.

Discussion

The study, conducted over six months with 200 pregnant women diagnosed with (GDM), revealed significant findings. The participants had an average age of 29.5 years and a mean BMI of 27.8 kg/m², with 40% being first-time mothers. Key risk factors included a family history of diabetes (30%) and previous GDM (20%), while 15% had polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS) and 12.5% had hypertension. Blood glucose levels showed a mean fasting glucose of 95.2 mg/dL and a 2-hour post-OGTT level of 153.4 mg/dL. Maternal outcomes indicated that 25% required insulin therapy, 10%

developed hypertensive disorders, and 30% had cesarean deliveries. Fetal outcomes were generally positive, with an average birth weight of 3.2 kg, though 5% had low Apgar scores, 7.5% experienced neonatal hypoglycemia, and 10% needed NICU admission. Significant associations were found between GDM and both family history of diabetes (p=0.03) and previous GDM (p=0.01), highlighting the importance of these risk factors in the development of GDM. These findings underscore the necessity for targeted screening and management strategies to improve maternal and fetal health outcomes in GDM cases.

3,034 pregnant women in Nepal were found to have a lower prevalence of GDM (3.42%). A family history of diabetes and advanced maternal age were important risk factors. The study also showed that polyhydramnios and increased rates of caesarean sections were prevalent obstetric problems [4]. A retrospective research conducted in Tamil Nadu, India, revealed that 35.8% of 530 pregnant women had GDM. The majority of

diagnoses were made by fasting plasma glucose testing, and advanced maternal age and obesity were important risk factors [5].

A research conducted in Bhubaneswar, India, on 218 pregnant women revealed a 13.8% prevalence of GDM. A family history of diabetes, a higher body mass index (BMI), and an older mother were important risk factors. Significant maternal and newborn problems, including polyhydramnios, postpartum haemorrhage, and premature delivery, were also found to be linked to GDM [6]. A study of 735 pregnant women in Kolkata, India, found that 17.2% of them had GDM. Maternal age, a family history of diabetes, and indicators like reactive oxygen species (ROS) and DNA damage were found to be important risk factors. Notably, it was discovered that inflammation and oxidative stress, separate from obesity, play a major role in the pathophysiology of GDM [7].

Conclusion

In a tertiary care context, this study offers important insights into the demographic traits, risk factors, and outcomes related to GDM. The results highlight the value of focused screening and management techniques to enhance the health of both the mother and the foetus in GDM patients.

References

1. Huhn EA, Rossi SW, Hoesli I, Göbl CS. Controversies in screening and diagnostic criteria for gestational diabetes in early and late pregnancy. *Frontiers in endocrinology*. 2018 Nov 27;9:696.
2. McIntyre HD, Catalano P, Zhang C, Desoye G, Mathiesen ER, Damm P. Gestational diabetes mellitus. *Nature reviews Disease primers*. 2019 Jul 11;5(1):47.
3. Shah NS, Wang MC, Freaney PM, Perak AM, Carnethon MR, Kandula NR, Gunderson EP, Bullard KM, Grobman WA, O'Brien MJ, Khan SS. Trends in gestational diabetes at first live birth by race and ethnicity in the US, 2011-2019. *Jama*. 2021 Aug 17;326(7):660-9.
4. Singh S, Yadav M. Gestational Diabetes Mellitus among Pregnant Women Delivering in a Tertiary Care Hospital: A Descriptive Cross-sectional Study. *JNMA: Journal of the Nepal Medical Association*. 2022 Mar;60(247):229.
5. Kumar CN, Manova VB, Maniyarasi R, Paveena V, Vanitha K. Prevalance and Risk Factors of Gestational Diabetes Mellitus: A Retrospective Study. *Prof. (Dr) RK Sharma*. 20 20 Apr;20(2):242.
6. Panigrahi A, Mallicka, Panda J. Gestational diabetes mellitus, its associated factors, and the pregnancy outcomes among pregnant women attending tertiary care hospitals of Bhubaneswar, India. *International Journal of Diabetes in Developing Countries*. 2020 Sep; 40:371-8.
7. Basu J, Datta C, Chowdhury S, Mandal D, Mondal NK, Ghosh A. Gestational diabetes mellitus in a tertiary care hospital of Kolkata, India: prevalence, pathogenesis and potential disease biomarkers. *Experimental and clinical endocrinology & diabetes*. 2020 Apr;128 (04) :216-23.